

LINGUOCOGNITIVE FACTORS OF THE BASIS OF SIMILES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses similes, which form the basis of our speech, and their role in human cognitive activity. Additionally, the linguocognitive factors of the basis of similes are explored and illustrated with examples. It should be noted that similes have a direct impact on human cognitive activity. They help generate new ideas, organize existing knowledge, and simplify complex concepts.

Introduction: Today, cognitive linguistics is a very important and increasingly significant field, as it studies the language of human thinking and the processes of perceiving the world in close interconnection. This contributes to a more practical understanding of language issues, placing them at the center of attention from the perspective of humanity. According to A.Rahimova, a cognitive approach to language learning is being formed. This approach involves analyzing the specific characteristics of how a person acquires, stores, and transmits knowledge. Special attention is paid to the process of transmitting knowledge through language, as well as to the role of language as a means of understanding the surrounding reality. As Maslova points out, the main branches developing within the framework of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics are cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology. In cognitology, human activity is considered, first and foremost, as a system of receiving, processing, storing information, and using this information in accordance with the situation. [Maslova, 2004].

In his monograph "Cognitive Linguistics," Sh.Safarov asserts that the main task of cognitive linguistics is to study the mental processes occurring in the human mind in connection with linguistic activity. In this regard, one of the main achievements of this science is the collection of information about the "traces" of previous experience formed in memory as a result of human cognitive activity, that is, categorical concepts and logical and linguistic systems of high-level structures of various types. The continuity of the connection between these two systems is clearly reflected in the phenomenon of categorization [Safarov, 2006].

METHODS

The methods of classification, description, and lexico-semantic analysis were effectively employed in the presentation of this article. The descriptive method is considered one of the primary analytical approaches in elucidating the nature of comparisons and their role in human cognitive activity. Through lexico-semantic analysis, the units that form the basis of comparison were identified.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is known that one of the main functions of language is the communicativeness. However, in the process of conversation, people try not only to exchange ideas but also to express their attitudes towards the events of reality. The words in our vocabulary not only name objects and phenomena but also express the speaker's attitude to the expressed thought and their own assessment. This relationship encompasses various emotional responses, such as affection, anger, hatred, admiration, irony, and surprise. It is difficult to imagine our speech without similes. Similes help us understand the linguistic picture of the world. Understanding the linguistic picture of the world is important for humanity's comprehension of the world, exchange of connections, and understanding of social life. By studying the various features of language, we can gain more information about our lives, society, and the whole world. The human mind perceives, processes, and evaluates objects and phenomena in the environment through comparison, analogy, and similarity. As events occurring in the objective world, social processes, things and objects, thoughts and experiences are compared and perceived, the process of cognition is somewhat simplified. That is, through comparison, new knowledge and unfamiliar phenomena are linked to existing knowledge in our language, and the possibility of imagination is clarified. Based on this, processes such as the systematization and grouping of existing knowledge occurring in our consciousness can also be considered cognitive activities based on comparisons and analogies.

Cognitive linguistics focuses not only on language itself but also on how language reflects the ways and means of understanding the world around us and processing information obtained from it. Thus, all linguistic phenomena and processes provide access to knowledge about reality and reflect people's understanding of the world. This indicates that a cognitive approach to similes, which are an important category in the cognitive process, can yield significant conclusions and facts for modern linguistics. Simile constructions express the unique national-cultural perspectives of people's perception of the world. As products of a nation's figurative way of thinking, stabilized, standardized images reflect national perception [Mahmudov, Khudoyberganova, 2013].

Forms and types of comparison are closely linked to characteristics of national consciousness and national thinking. Correct interpretation of an entire text often depends on properly understanding comparisons, since, as we have shown, comparisons are involved not only in cognitive processes but also in imagining, describing, classifying, and evaluating subjects/objects, often manifesting as an emotional-expressive method. Comparison is a distinct unit of cognitive processes, an operational thinking unit involved in forming and expressing thoughts [Van Yalun, 2002].

Comparison is a specific component of the language system. One could say that an explicit simile in a text or speech is merely the visible part of a tree, its tip, while the process of forming a simile is like the deeply hidden roots of that imaginary tree, nourished by the soil in which it grows. In other words, comparison is closely tied to characteristics of national consciousness and national thinking [Van Yalun, 2002].

The emergence of comparative expressions in speech thinking activities (both everyday and artistic) is closely connected to the ontological essence of logical-semantic structures and their role in understanding reality. Arguably, no rational action is possible without

comparisons. Comparisons form the basis of speech thinking in word creativity. Comparative constructions are a unique objectification of the hidden processes of poetic cognition of the surrounding world, as the associative connections reflected in them are based on a person's clear ideas about what is already known and newly learned. Moreover, the distinctive feature of comparisons is the interconnection of fundamentally different concepts and entire situations, and it is this "distance" that creates broad opportunities for the interpretive methodology of poetic thinking. [Gennadevna, 2012].

Through analogies, people learn how to perceive the world and what representations and models to use. Comparisons perform the following functions in human cognitive activity:

According to linguist F.Usmanov, the linguistic landscape created by a language community is a kind of subjective world. It is simpler and more vivid than the material world, facilitating the process of perceiving and naming elements of the objective world. Figurative comparisons acquire linguocultural significance by representing objects and phenomena in a nationally conditioned linguistic image, comparing them to other objects based on their properties [Usmanov, 2020]. Comparisons are an important means of communication. They help express complex thoughts in a simple and understandable way, allowing for quick and effective conveyance of ideas to others. Similarly, similes play a crucial role in understanding abstract concepts. We compare abstract concepts with concrete things, making them easier to comprehend. *For example: As Zebi, carrying the bedding to the courtyard, listened to these sorrows, she was amazed by the poor mother's mountain-like endurance [Cholpon. Night and Day].* In this sentence, a person's ability to endure grief, exercise patience, and remain content is compared to a mountain. We know that mountains are considered very tall, strong elements of nature. The semes of "strength" and "vastness" in mountains serve as the basis for this comparison.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the linguocognitive analysis of similes serves to express human cognitive processes, emotions, and worldviews through linguistic means. Writers, using similes, transform simple images into complex, figurative, and emotionally expressive artistic images.

Through comparison, it becomes possible to identify similarities between two different things or phenomena and establish connections between them. This activates cognitive processes and paves the way for acquiring new knowledge. Additionally, by expanding the pictorial and expressive possibilities of language, it helps deepen people's understanding of the world and enables them to convey it to others more accurately and effectively.

References:

1. Ван Яньлун. Онимы в функции сравнения: Автореф. дис. ... кандидат филол. наук. – Москва. 2002. – С. 144.
2. Геннадьевна. П.И. Сравнение как дискурсивно-стилистическая фигура региональной когнитивной поэтики. Дисс. ... канд. Филол. наук. – Белгород, 2012. – С. 204.
3. Маслова В.А. Когнитивная лингвистика. – Минск: Тетрасистемс, 2004. – С. 256.
4. Махмудов Н., Худойбергана Д. Ўзбек тили ўхшатишларининг изоҳли луғати. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2013. –Б. 320.
5. Рахимова.А.Р. Вербализация характера и эмоционального состояния человека в устойчивых сравнениях русского языка: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Казан. 2018. – С. 199.
6. Safarov Sh. Kognitiv tilshunoslik. – Jizzax: Sangzor, 2006. – 91 b.
7. Усманов Ф. Ўзбек тилидаги ўхшатишларнинг лингвомаданий тадқиқи. Филол. фан. фал. док (PhD) ...дисс. – Тошкент, 2020. – 173 б.
8. Cho'lpon. "Kecha va Kunduz". – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2013. – B. 332.